

Comparative Physico-chemical analysis of Shivnath river Durg (C.G.) state of India

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ABSTRACT

Shivnath River is the major tributary of the Mahanadi which is the chief river of Durg district. The present research work were conducted in three different sites of Shivnath river ie- Mahamara annicut (S1), Sagnighat (S2) and Patharia (S3) of Durg district (C.G.). Sample collection was performed during the year December 2024 and collected water was analyzed for the various physicochemical parameters like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), Total dissolved solids (TDS), Total hardness, alkalinity and concentration of elements or ions such as Ca, Mg, sulphates, nitrates etc. as per the standard guidelines provided by the central pollution board, New Delhi, APHE, BIS and WHO for downstream river water bodies of the above three sites. The above parameters help in determination of the water quality index of the river water. The results revealed that maximum concentration of various factors like temperature (24.4⁰C), pH (8.9), turbidity (6.9 mg/l), BOD (13 mg/l), TDS(215 mg/l) and comparatively all other parameters were found to be maximum in the Patharia (S3) resulting in lowest dissolved oxygen rate DO (4.40 mg/l) due to deposition of the pollutants and organic matter, however sufficient amount of impurities were also observed in the other two sites which clearly indicates that the water quality and characteristics is affected. Thus the physicochemical as well as water quality assessment studies clearly suggested the water quality index, unsafe for human consumption and required proper water quality treatment to protect such an important biological resources like water bodies which is exploited continuously due to human activities, industrialization, urbanization and many other activities. Such study enables us to understand the requirements like periodic water monitoring, measures for restoration of water bodies as well as to formulate many river action plans for upgradation of the quality of the river water bodies.

Therefore the present study aims to do the comparative physicochemical analysis of the three different sites S1, S2, S3 of Shivnath River Durg C.G.

KEYWORDS: Industrialization, Water quality, urbanization, Shivnath River.

INTRODUCTION

Water is very important biological resource, play vital role for all living organisms, including plants, animals and humans. It comprises 70.9% of earth surface, 96.5% oceans, 1.7% glaciers and ice caps of Antarctica and Greenland, and 0.001% in the form of vapour, clouds and precipitation. Therefore earth water consists only of 2.5% of fresh water. (Shukla, *et al.*, 2015).

The river Mahanadi is the most important river also known as lifeline of Chhattisgarh. Shivnath river is the second important as well as main tributary of Mahanadi river.(Belorkar,&Seema). It comprises total length of 290 km.(Shukla, *et al.*,2015). This river is very important source because it supplies water to many industries as well as drinking water to many districts of Chhattisgarh.(Singh and Jain, 2020).

Chhattisgarh has rich heritage of natural resources like coal, bauxite, iron, limestone and many other precious stones and due to the presence of these richest raw material Durg district has been developed as an industrial hub. Many industries like brick plants, cement factories are situated near the bank of river. Such an important biological resource is now being polluted due to the continuous discharge of domestic and industrial waste directly into the water bodies, harming the aquatic flora and fauna also. (singh and jain, 2020). There is an abundant reservoir of fresh water reserves and ground water reserves in India. But 70% of these surface water resources are contaminating due to biological toxic, organic and inorganic pollutants. The average annual freshwater was 5177 cubic meters and it reaches up to 1140 cum by 2050. (Singh and Shrivastava, 2014). Moreover excessive use of pesticides and fertilizers also leads to deterioration of fresh water bodies as well as dumping of untreated municipal as industrial wastes directly into natural water bodies. (Bhadja and Vaghela, 2013).

Water is such a precious biological reserve which is continuously exploited due to increasing population and urbanization and is a major concern for water engineers and planners to formulate effective strategies and model for sustainable water resource management. Thus water should be

hygienic and it should be free from impurities as well as safe for consumption and survival of organisms. (CPCB,2009).

So keeping the above point in mind and to protect, conserve these precious biological resources, study of good water conservation techniques and water treatments methods are essential to maintain the standard quality of water. Therefore in the present study physico-chemical analysis of shivnath river were performed for safe consumption and conservation of important biological resource.

SELECTION OF SAMPLING POINT:

The research work was conducted in shivnath river Durg dist. (C.G.) India. Sample was collected from three different sites of shivnath river Durg. The sites were Mehamara anicut (S1), Sagnighat (S2), and Patharia (S3) of Durg dist. (C.G.). Mahamara is surrounded by temples, Muktidham as well as water treatment plant is also located. Sagnighat has famous religious, agricultural and picnic spot. The third sampling site was Patharia which is surrounded by agricultural land, stone mining spots, brick forming industries. Due to domestic, sewage disposal and continuous discharge by industries, such an important water resource is being exploited, thereby making it unsafe for human consumption. Therefore physico chemical analysis of the river water of the above three sites were performed in these research work.

METHODOLOGY

Water samples were collected from the study sites using plastic bottles of 1000 ml capacity through Grab sampling process. Plastic bottles were labelled properly including the stream sites, collection time and date. Before collection of water sample, the bottles should be rinsed twice with the same water samples to be analysed. Finally the water sample was collected in the same manner from rest of the sites also and sealed properly. Samples collected were kept under normal room temperature and subjected to various physicochemical analysis.(Matthew, 2012). The analysis was performed as per the standard protocol of APHA and water quality is compared with the standards of central pollution control board, New Delhi, APHE, WHO, and BIS. (, Shukl *et al.*, 2015; singh and jain, 2020; Belorkar, CPCB, 2009). The physicochemical properties

of collected water samples were performed within 24 hours of collection and data was listed in the table given below.(APHA, BIS, Garg 2010).

Table 1: Comparative Physico- chemical parameters of river waters of the selected study sites (CPCS standards) with standard value.

S.N.	Characteristics	Unit of Measurement	BIS	WHO	S1	S2	S3
1.	Color	300 Harzen units	5	5	Nil	Nil	Nil
2.	Taste	-	-	-	Ni	Nil	Nil
3.	Odour	-	-	-	Nil	Nil	Nil
4.	Temperature °C	°C	-	-	24.3	24.7	24.4
5.	Turbidity	N.T.U.	1	5	6.2	6.4	6.9
6.	pH	pH scale	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	8.4	8.7	8.9
7.	DO	mg/l	4-6ppm	4-6ppm	4.55	4.45	4.40
8.	BOD	mg/l	3	2	11	12	13
9.	TDS	mg/l	500		205	210	215
10.	Total Hardness	mg/l	200	500	188	193	197
11.	Total Alkalinity	mg/l	200	75	196	205	210
12.	Calcium	mg/l	75	75	74.5	75.8	77.4
13.	Magnesium	mg/l	30	50	9.8	9.9	10.1
14.	Nitrates	mg/l	45	45	32	33	35
15.	Sulphates	mg/l	200	200	15	16	17

Fig.1: Graphical representation between sampling station and parameters

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

During the present investigation, the following parameters of down stream rivers of three different sites that is Mehamara anicut (S1), Sagni ghat (S2) and Patharia (S3) were observed. Physico-chemical parameters like temperature , turbidity, pH, DO, BOD,TDS, Total hardness, and alkalinity were analysed as well as compared between the three different sites of the downstream water bodies.

Temperature: Maximum temperature recorded were 24.7⁰C in S2, followed by 24.4⁰C in S3 and least in S1 ie- 24.3⁰C. The above values are suitable for aquatic life and household activities according to the standards of (WHO,2017& 1972); (DPHE,2019); (USEPA,2012), (DOE,1997).(Rahaman *et al.*, 2021).The increase or decrease in the rate of temperature will influence the decomposition rate by micro organisms.(Thomas,1991);(Sahu *et al.*, 2022).The DO is affected by temperature of polluted water.(Machender *et al.*, 2013; Ahmed *et al.*, 2016; Rahman *et al.*, 2021). The dissolved oxygen content reduces sharply with increase in temperature. Our data shows similar results where the DO content was 4.40 mg/l in S3 with temperature of 24.4⁰C. Hence the temperature affects the dissolved oxygen. (Kaiser *et al.*, 2006).

pH & Alkalinity/Total Hardness: The pH recorded by S3 was 8.9 followed by S2 - 8.7 and least pH was 8.4 -S1.pH and alkalinity both factors influence each other.pH is also a crucial parameter for water quality assessment which increases the solubility of phosphorus and nitrates making them more accessible for plant growth and increasing the demand for dissolved oxygen which ultimately increases the BOD content.(Hem, 1989; Zhang, 2010; Sahu *et al.*, 2022).Low pH indicates decomposition of organic matter.(Hem,1989). The normal range of pH for surface water systems is 6.5-8.5 and for irrigation and fish culture is from 6.5-8.0.

Whereas the total alkalinity recorded were S3(210), S2(205),S1(196).(BIS,WHO). Similar results of TA range between 165-302 mg/l were reported by Rahman *et al.*, 2021.In Our findings the TA value ranges between 196 to 210mg/l. The observed TA values of the shivnath river water was found to be higher than those of permissible limit of standard .(Afrin *et al.*, 2015; Rahman *et al.*, 2021) which may be due to the effluents from the industry, factories that are responsible for the TA increase in urban river water.(Sharma, 2003).

Total Hardness values were found to be maximum in S3(197), S2(193), S1(188).The TH concentration range below 75 mg/l of the river water are considered as soft, 75-150mg/l (moderately hard), 150-300mg/l (hard), more than 300mg/l (very hard).(Sawyer and Mc Carty, 1967; Rahman *et al.*, 2021). With relevance to above data the river water of the study site was considered as hard indicating that the river water was not suitable for different household activities and drinking.Thus it was clear that with increase in total hardness, the total alkalinity as well as pH also increases resulting in low DO.(Sahu *et al.*, 2022).

Turbidity and TDS: Turbidity recorded was 6.9 (S3), followed by 6.4 (S2) and 6.2 (S1).(BIS, WHO)A significant increase in the amount of TDS were observed in S3 (215), S2 (210) followed by S1 (205).(BIS, WHO).The TDS concentration of the collected river water samples was within the range of 205 to 215mg/l. The maximum limits of TDS for drinking water are 600, 500 and 600 mg/l respectively.(WHO, 2017; USEPA, 2012; DPHE, 2019).TDS limit for irrigation is 2000 mg/l.Hence it can be stated that the river water is unsuitable for domestic purposes such as drinking, bathing.(DOE, 1997); Rahman *et al.*, 2021). Additionally high TDS load cannot effectively reduce the nutrient load of urban waste water, which leads to deterioration of the quality of the river water.(Brar *et al.*, 2017; Rahman *et al.*, 2021).

DO/BOD: The Dissolved oxygen values were found to be maximum in S1(4.55 mg/l) followed by S2(4.45 mg/l), and least in S3(4.40 mg/l). The values of BOD ranges from S3(13 mg/l), S2(12 mg/l), S1(11 mg/l). Biological oxygen demand and dissolved oxygen are influenced by the factors like total solids, alkalinity, nitrite, pH, conductivity, water temperature.(Verma, Singh, 2013; Sahu *et al.*, 2022).. Similarly with increase in alkalinity content, total dissolve solids increases, which directly increases the BOD.(Radtke *et al.*, 2005; Sahu *et al.*, 2022). The DO value between 0 to 2.40 mg/l is unfit for the survival of aquatic life.(Uddin and Jeong, 2021). The standard DO concentration are 6mg/l for drinking water, 4-5 mg/l for entertainment, 4-6 mg/l for fish and domesticated animals and 5mg/l for industrial applications.(WHO, 2017; DOE, 1997; DPHE, 2019; Rahman *et al.*, 2021). The industrial effluents as well as municipal waste demands much oxygen for chemical oxidation and decomposition.(Whitehead *et al.*, 2018). The deficiency of oxygen, nutrients availability and increased organic substances increases pathogens in water.(Whitehead *et al.*, 2018; Rahman *et al.*, 2021).The growth and decay of floating and submerged aquatic microphytes further contributes to high oxygen demand by the microorganism and decrease in DO level.(Hasan *et al.*, 2019; Rahman *et al.*, 2021). . A BOD concentration of 13-73 mg/l near an industrial area was recorded by Aktar *et al.*, 2017. These findings are similar to our work where BOD value ranges from 11 mg/l to 13 mg/l was recorded in the river water sample..

Calcium, Magnesium, nitrates & Sulphates: Test results showed that maximum calcium concentration were recorded from S3 (77.4), followed by S2 (75.8), and least by S1(74.5). Similarly magnesium concentration recorded were 10.1(S3), 9.9 (S2), 9.8 (S1). Maximum nitrates concentration obtained from S3 (35), S2 (33), S1(32). And accordingly the concentration of sulphate were found to be maximum in S3(17), S2(16), S1(15).(BIS, WHO).(Shukla *et al.*, 2015). The results showed that the nitrate concentration of site S3 was 35 with DO value of 4.40 which showed the decreased DO value with respect to increased nitrate concentration. Nitrates are essential nutrients for the plants which can cause plants and algae to grow rapidly in any river and leads to high BOD levels and depletion of Oxygen.(Poulsen *et al.*, 2018); Sahu *et al.*, 2022).

Nitrite is extremely toxic to aquatic life but it rapidly oxidizes to nitrate which is responsible for the growth of water hyacinth covering the surface of river water making it difficult for sunlight

to reach beneath the water surface decreasing the rate of aeration and in turn the DO demand increases. (Gary, 1985).

CONCLUSION

The result from comparative study of different parameters from all the three sites ie- S1, S2, S3 showed that the water sample collected from Patharia (S3) of Durg district .C.G were found to have maximum concentration of all parameters like pH (8.9), turbidity (6.9), BOD (13), TDS (215), Hardness (197), alkalinity (210) as well as the other elements concentrations like Ca (77.4), Mg (10.1), Nitrate (35), Sulphate (17) as compared to other two sites ie- Mehamara (S1) and Sagnihat (S2). However appropriate concentration of these elements like Ca, Mg, TDS were also found to be present in Mehamara and Sagnihat. Thus it became very much clear from the data that with increasing distance biological oxygen demand increases due to increased pollutants and many other impurities suspended in the water bodies and thus dissolved oxygen content decreases. Thus it became very much clear from the recorded data that the river water bodies of the three sites is polluted due to organic loading especially from the domestic waste from durg city and the residential colonies of industries due to high level of BOD. These value of water quality index are clearly showing that water sources of study area are polluted because of all kinds of discharges from various sources. Rapid economical development, poses serious threats to the environment and one of the major threat is pollution of the important water reservoirs. Water quality index of Shivnath river is continuously degraded due to industrialization, urbanization, mining, anthropogenic activities and various other activities are responsible for polluting the river water bodies thereby disturbing the ecosystem and several life forms. The quality of water can be measured by various parameters like temperature, pH, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, Biological oxygen demand, nitrate, phosphate, sulphate and various metal ions. Compounds such as nitrates react with various compounds present in our body and form carcinogenic compounds. Sulphate gives a bitter taste to water (Singh & Jain, 2020). Turbidity of water increases due to the suspended solids and planktons in the water bodies which increase the cloudiness of water and higher level of turbidity pose threat to the several life forms. Temperature of water is an important parameter for controlling the metabolic activities, reproductive activities and thereby controlling the aquatic life. Similarly pH of water is too

important factor because increased acidic or basic concentration may disrupt the whole ecosystem especially the aquatic organisms (Singh & Jain, 2020). Due to the increased pollutants in the water bodies, biological oxygen demand increases which clearly suggests increased microbial growth in the water bodies.

Therefore immediate action should be taken for water quality restoration. water quality management treatment studies should be performed. Moreover various action plans like plantation of trees, recycling of waste, proper sewage treatment, water pollution control programs and many public awareness programs can be undertaken to overcome these serious problem.Hence from the above research work, it can be concluded that significant amount of impurities and precipitates were found to be present in the water bodies of the three sites of shivnath river which clearly indicates the quality of the river water and thus it requires proper management and conservation.

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